

Characteristics of sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease

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Abstract

1. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder. In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to non-motor symptoms, particularly sleep disturbances, which significantly affect patients' quality of life. These include insomnia, excessive daytime sleepiness, rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder, obstructive sleep apnoea, and restless legs syndrome. The aim of this study is to review current literature concerning the relationship between sleep disorders and Parkinson's disease.

2. REVIEW METHODS

A narrative review of publications indexed in the PubMed and Google Scholar databases was conducted. Priority was given to studies published between 2017 and 2025, although earlier key publications were included when justified. Original research articles, meta-analyses, review papers, and current classifications of sleep disorders were analysed.

3. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF CURRENT KNOWLEDGE

Sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease result from both neurodegenerative processes and dopaminergic treatment. Insomnia affects more than half of patients, while excessive daytime sleepiness increases with disease progression and pharmacotherapy. REM sleep behaviour disorder often precedes motor symptoms. Obstructive sleep apnoea demonstrates a bidirectional relationship with PD, and restless legs syndrome occurs more frequently than in the general population. Dopaminergic medications may have both beneficial and adverse effects on sleep.

4. CONCLUSION

Sleep disorders are common in Parkinson's disease and significantly reduce quality of life. Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment may improve patient functioning and potentially slow disease progression.

Keywords— Parkinson's disease, sleep disorders, sleep, neurodegenerative diseases

Introduction and Aim of the Study

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder and is characterised by progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the pars compacta of the substantia nigra in the midbrain [1–3]. As a consequence of this process, patients develop characteristic motor symptoms, including bradykinesia, muscular rigidity, resting tremor, and postural and gait disturbances. Although motor symptoms form the basis of clinical diagnosis, contemporary research indicates that the clinical picture of Parkinson's disease is considerably more complex and involves widespread structural and functional changes in multiple brain regions [2,4–6].

In recent years, increasing attention has been devoted to non-motor symptoms, which often appear long before the onset of classical motor manifestations. The most frequently observed include olfactory dysfunction, cognitive impairment, and autonomic nervous system dysfunction. These symptoms significantly reduce patients' quality of life and negatively affect social functioning through changes in behaviour, affect, and personality [1,2,4,5].

In older patients, treatment of Parkinson's disease is typically initiated with gradually increasing doses of levodopa in order to reduce the risk of dyskinesias. In younger patients, dopamine agonists and monoamine oxidase type B inhibitors are more commonly used, as they reduce the risk of motor fluctuations and provide better control of levodopa-resistant tremor. In selected cases, anticholinergic drugs may also be added [6]. In advanced stages of the disease, when motor fluctuations and dyskinesias persist despite combination pharmacotherapy, advanced therapies are employed. These include deep-brain stimulation and continuous infusions of apomorphine or levodopa. Such approaches provide more stable dopaminergic stimulation and improved symptom control [7].

To date, at least five key mechanisms contributing to dopaminergic neuronal death in Parkinson's disease have been identified. These include proteasomal dysfunction, mitochondrial dysfunction, increased oxidative stress, aggregation of α -synuclein oligomers, and abnormalities in lysosomal autophagy. It is believed that the primary determinants of disease development include genetic factors, environmental influences, and ageing-related processes [2,8].

Sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease are common and heterogeneous. They include, among others, insomnia, excessive daytime sleepiness, nightmares, rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder (RBD), obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA), and restless legs syndrome (RLS). These disturbances may result from neurodegenerative changes in sleep-regulating centres and from the effects of pharmacological treatment. They may appear during the prodromal phase and in the early stages of PD, with their prevalence increasing systematically as the disease progresses. Sleep disorders may occur in isolation or coexist with one another. Their presence significantly worsens quality of life and may represent an early marker of disease development [2,5,9,10]. Available evidence indicates that circadian rhythm disturbances in patients with PD are complex

and multifactorial; therefore, thorough clinical and instrumental assessment (e.g. actigraphy, polysomnography) is required to identify the underlying cause and implement appropriate treatment [1].

Understanding the significance of sleep disorders in the course of Parkinson's disease is crucial for improving patients' quality of life, enabling earlier diagnosis, and advancing knowledge of the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying this complex condition. Therefore, the aim of this study is to review current scientific publications concerning the relationship between sleep and Parkinson's disease.

Methods of the Review

The literature review was conducted using the PubMed and Google Scholar databases. Publications from the years 2017–2025 were included, with older sources incorporated when justified. Search terms related to sleep disorders in Parkinson's disease were used. Peer-reviewed original articles, meta-analyses, review papers, and current classifications of sleep disorders were included. Studies of low methodological quality, case reports, popular science publications, and articles not meeting thematic or scientific criteria were excluded.

Physiology of Sleep

Sleep is a biological process with a complex structure that occurs cyclically and comprises two main phases: non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep and rapid eye movement (REM) sleep. Sleep begins with NREM stages, which are divided into three progressively deepening stages, ranging from light sleep (stages 1 and 2) to deep sleep (stage 3). During NREM sleep, reduced muscle tone, decreased blood pressure and body temperature, and a slowing of heart rate are observed, contributing to bodily regeneration [11–13].

Approximately 70–100 minutes after sleep onset, the transition to REM sleep occurs, also referred to as paradoxical sleep. This phase is characterised by high brain activity, rapid eye movements, near-complete muscle atonia, and vivid dreaming. As the night progresses, REM sleep episodes gradually lengthen and may account for up to approximately 30% of total sleep time in the final cycles [11,13,14].

In adults, a complete sleep cycle is repeated on average four to five times per night and lasts between 90 and 120 minutes. Approximately 75–80% of total sleep time is spent in NREM sleep, while 20–25% occurs during REM sleep. Proper sleep architecture is essential for maintaining cognitive function, emotional balance, immune processes, hormonal regulation, and bodily repair mechanisms. Disruptions in sleep cyclicality may lead to deterioration in well-being, cognitive performance, and overall health status [11–13].

Insomnia in Parkinson's Disease

Insomnia is one of the most common sleep disorders in patients with PD and represents a significant component of the clinical picture of the disease [10,15,16]. It most frequently manifests as difficulty maintaining sleep, frequent nocturnal awakenings, and a subjective sense of non-restorative, fragmented sleep. As the disease progresses, these complaints tend to intensify, whereas difficulties with sleep initiation are reported less frequently [15,17,18]. Insomnia is a common symptom in PD, with studies indicating that it may affect more than half of patients and occurs more frequently in women [19].

Insomnia is associated with adverse clinical consequences. Patients suffering from insomnia more often report gastrointestinal symptoms, circadian rhythm disturbances, and non-motor symptoms, including autonomic dysfunction [1,20]. Other parasomnias, such as RLS and RBD, frequently coexist, further impairing sleep quality [9].

In patients with PD, insomnia may lead to reduced quality of life, increased severity of depressive and anxiety symptoms, and impaired daytime functioning [9,17,18]. Dopaminergic therapies may also contribute significantly to the occurrence of insomnia. Although effective in alleviating motor symptoms, these medications may increase the risk of sleep disturbances, exacerbate daytime sleepiness, and interfere with nocturnal sleep maintenance [20,21].

Chronic insomnia may exacerbate both motor and non-motor symptoms and therefore represents an important therapeutic challenge in PD. Current treatment options include pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches. Pharmacological treatments include melatonin, melatonin receptor agonists, orexin receptor antagonists, and benzodiazepines. Non-pharmacological interventions encompass cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia, light therapy, deep brain stimulation, and non-invasive brain stimulation techniques [17,20].

Excessive Daytime Sleepiness in Parkinson's Disease

Excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS) is a common symptom in PD and is characterised by difficulty maintaining wakefulness and alertness during typical daytime situations, resulting in uncontrollable episodes of sleep. EDS represents a significant health risk for patients with PD, markedly impairs daily functioning, and increases the risk of motor vehicle accidents, particularly during driving [22–24].

It is estimated that EDS affects approximately 16–55% of patients with PD, with severity increasing alongside disease duration and progression [25,26]. Prospective studies support this trend. In a study conducted by Amara et al. in 2017 involving a cohort of 423 patients with early-stage PD, the mean Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) score increased significantly from 5.8 ± 3.5 to 7.55 ± 4.6 over a three-year follow-up period. Additionally, the proportion of patients with EDS increased as the disease progressed [25]. In the same study, EDS was associated with a non-tremor-dominant PD phenotype, autonomic dysfunction, depression, and anxiety, but was not associated with increased motor impairment [25].

Xiang et al. conducted a study involving 1,221 patients with PD, with a mean age of 61.5 ± 9.9 years; 54.1% were women and 45.9% were men. The study demonstrated that patients with EDS were older than those without this condition. The EDS group also showed a higher prevalence of alcohol consumption, older age at PD onset, longer disease duration, and lower educational attainment. No significant differences were observed between groups with respect to smoking status, tea consumption, pesticide exposure, body mass index, or levodopa dosage [27].

Both the disease itself and pharmacological treatment may contribute to the development of EDS [22,25,27]. Patients with EDS also exhibit more severe PD symptoms, which may be associated with greater damage to brain structures involved in the regulation of wakefulness [24,27].

REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder in Parkinson's Disease

REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) is a parasomnia characterised by loss of physiological muscle atonia during REM sleep and enactment of dreams. These behaviours are often violent and may include punching, kicking, and thrashing movements, frequently accompanied by vocalisations such as shouting or screaming [28–30].

Since its first description in 1986, RBD has increasingly been recognised as an important prodromal marker of neurodegenerative diseases, particularly PD [31,32]. It is estimated to occur in 35–60% of patients with PD, and symptoms may precede motor manifestations such as tremor, rigidity, and bradykinesia [1,28,29,33].

Clinical studies have shown that RBD occurs more frequently in patients with the akinetic-rigid subtype of PD, which is characterised by the absence of tremor dominance, more frequent gait disturbances, and significant impairment of autonomic and cognitive functions [29,32,33]. In prospective cohorts, patients with PD and RBD exhibited faster progression of motor symptoms and a higher risk of developing dementia [30,33].

Polysomnography is considered the gold standard for diagnosing RBD. A diagnosis can be established when REM sleep without atonia is demonstrated in accordance with the ICSD-3 criteria (International Classification of Sleep Disorders, Third Edition) [28,29]. RBD is regarded as an important risk factor and potential prodromal marker of PD, with its presence potentially preceding the onset of cognitive impairment by many years or even decades [29,30,33].

Restless Legs Syndrome in Parkinson's Disease

Restless legs syndrome (RLS), also known as Willis–Ekbom disease, is a sensorimotor disorder characterised by an urge to move the lower limbs. Symptoms typically occur at rest, predominantly in the evening or at night, and are relieved by movement. RLS coexists with conditions such as chronic kidney disease, arterial hypertension, and headache disorders [34–36].

Meta-analyses indicate that the prevalence of RLS in patients with PD is approximately 14%, with slightly lower rates reported in Asian populations (12%) compared with non-Asian populations (16%) [34,36]. The risk of RLS is significantly higher in patients with PD than in the healthy population [34,37]. Additionally, cohort studies have suggested that RLS may increase the risk of later development of PD, and the response to dopaminergic treatment supports the involvement of dopaminergic pathway dysfunction [34,35].

Patients with coexisting PD and RLS demonstrate greater severity of non-motor symptoms, sleep disturbances, and pain symptoms. In patients with PD, the coexistence of RLS and reduced sleep quality is associated with more severe RLS symptoms, which translates into poorer quality of life [37,38]. Furthermore, iron deficiency may additionally contribute to the pathogenesis of RLS [34,39].

Despite the growing body of epidemiological and clinical data, there remains a lack of conclusive evidence as to whether RLS represents a prodromal symptom of PD or develops secondarily during the course of the disease [35].

Obstructive Sleep Apnoea in Parkinson's Disease

Obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA) is a common and potentially treatable sleep disorder in PD that is increasingly being identified. In the general population, OSA occurs more frequently in men, affecting approximately one-third (34%), while nearly one in five women (17%) are affected. The prevalence of OSA in patients with PD is approximately twice that observed in the general population [40–42].

The literature emphasises that the relationship between OSA and PD may be bidirectional [41,43]. In individuals with OSA, recurrent apnoeic episodes lead to intermittent hypoxia, which promotes oxidative stress, inflammatory processes, and neuronal degeneration. These mechanisms may contribute to the accelerated progression of PD [44]. Moreover, sleep fragmentation and REM sleep disturbances may impair the functioning of the glymphatic system, which plays a crucial role in the clearance of toxic proteins such as α -synuclein [8,45].

Conversely, neurodegenerative changes within the brainstem, particularly in the medulla oblongata and pontine respiratory centres, may disrupt autonomic respiratory control, thereby exacerbating OSA symptoms [8,40]. Impaired coordination of pharyngeal muscles and reduced neural control of the upper airway in PD further promote upper airway collapse during sleep, intensifying obstructive sleep apnoea [40,42,46]. Patients with PD and comorbid OSA have been observed to exhibit higher apnoea–hypopnoea index (AHI) values, as well as more pronounced cognitive and motor symptoms [40].

Certain therapies used in the treatment of PD, such as levodopa, may further contribute to the increased prevalence of OSA [40]. The relationship between OSA and PD is bidirectional, with both conditions mutually exacerbating one another, resulting in deterioration of sleep quality, cognitive function, and overall quality of life [42,43].

Impact of Parkinson's Disease Medications on Sleep Disorders

Medications used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease, particularly dopaminergic agents, have a significant impact on the regulation of sleep and wakefulness. Although they effectively alleviate motor symptoms, their use may simultaneously increase the risk of sleep disturbances [1].

Factor / Drug Group	Impact on Sleep	References
Dopaminergic drugs (levodopa, dopamine agonists)	Excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS), sudden sleep episodes, and insomnia (paradoxical effect)	[17,22]
Antidepressant medications	Insomnia	[20,21]
Serotonergic drugs (especially antidepressants)	Increased risk of REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD)	[28]
Cognitive-enhancing medications	Insomnia	[20,21]
Dopaminergic therapy in RLS	Alleviation of RLS symptoms, improvement in sleep quality	[33]
OSA (obstructive sleep apnoea)	No association with the dose of dopaminergic medications	[38]

Tabela 1. The Impact of Medications and Clinical Factors on Sleep in Patients with Parkinson's Disease

The above table synthesises the most important associations between pharmacotherapy used in patients with Parkinson's disease (PD) and sleep disorders. Dopaminergic medications, despite their key role in the treatment of motor symptoms of PD, demonstrate a complex impact on sleep [17,20,21,22].

Summary

Sleep disorders represent a significant clinical problem in patients with Parkinson's disease and encompass a wide spectrum of symptoms, ranging from insomnia and excessive daytime sleepiness to REM sleep behaviour disorder, obstructive sleep apnoea, and restless legs syndrome. Their occurrence is associated both with progressive neurodegenerative changes in brain structures involved in sleep regulation and with the effects of dopaminergic pharmacotherapy.

These disorders often emerge as early as the prodromal phase and intensify with disease progression, significantly reducing patients' quality of life and adversely affecting cognitive, emotional, and social functioning.

Available evidence suggests that sleep disturbances may serve both as an early marker of PD development and as a factor modulating its further course. Appropriate diagnosis, based on clinical assessment and instrumental investigations such as polysomnography and actigraphy, enables the identification of specific sleep disorders and the selection of optimal pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment strategies. Early detection and management of sleep disorders in patients with PD is of crucial importance, as it may contribute to slowing disease progression.

Disclosure

All authors have read and agreed with the published version of the manuscript.

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Funding:

The study did not receive special funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement:

Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement:

Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement:

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest Statement:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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